

Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA Pipelines author list

Long Read team

Yousra Belattar, Hermione Blomfield-Smith, Tracey-jane Chillingworth, Craig Corton, Shelly-Ann Coutts, Alexander Dove, Mia Franulovic, Zoe Goate, Alexander Hatton, Carlos Jimenez Verdejo, Ifeoluwapo Joshua, Lucy Kitchin, William Knight, Tavis Mason, Robin Moll, Karen Oliver, Maariyah Rashid, Irene Fabiola Roman Maldonado, Mary-Ann Santosh, Michelle Smith, Emma Memune Taluy, John Tushabe, James Uphill, James Watts

Research and Development

Emma Betteridge, Iraad Bronner, Esther Mellado Gomez, Michael A. Quail, Diana Rajan, Nicholas Redshaw

Automation

Abby Crackett, Ben Farr, Chris Henderson, Lesley Shirley, Scott Thurston, Abdulrahman Tuameh

Team Lead for Illumina sequencing (Hi-C sequencing)

Tristram Bellerby

Data Quality Control

Paul Heath, James Mack, Henry Mallalieu, Neil Marriott, Elliott Trigg.

Technical administration

Alice Linsdell, Harriet Ninsiima

All authors: Wellcome Sanger Institute, Hinxton, Cambridgeshire CB10 1SA, UK